

BUSINESS MODEL OF ORGANIZING A JOINT BUSINESS IN CONVERGENCE

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Abstract: The article shows the business model of joint business organization within the framework of convergence and the modeling bases of convergence processes. In business organization, it is justified that convergence has a significant impact on the development of convergence of business companies. The business foundations of the convergence of regional districts have been developed in the conditions of the digital economy.

Keywords: Convergence framework, joint business organization, business model, convergence processes, divergence, optimal order, company merger, Financial convergence, system efficiency.

One of the most important issues of organizing a joint business within the framework of economic convergence is the form of its organization, that is, the option of interaction between the participants of this joint business. Finding the most effective option for conducting joint business (business models of economic convergence) in all sectors of the economy, including the insurance market, is very important to achieve a positive effect of the economic convergence process, first of all, to increase the competitiveness of the initiator. Therefore, for the insurance market, which are the main subjects of relations

For its effective development of insurance organizations, it is important to create the most effective business models of joint activity within the framework of economic convergence, both at the initiative of insurers and with their participation. A distinctive feature of the emerging banking and insurance groups, as well as bank holdings, is that banks and insurance companies in them increase their efficiency at the expense of guaranteed consumers of their services from any other spheres of economic and social life. This is one of the ways to increase the effectiveness of the activities of banks and insurance companies as organizational and organizational forms of business in the banking and insurance segments of the financial market. But financial market entities The task of increasing competitiveness forces us to look for other ways to increase their efficiency and competitiveness. Taking into account that financial services are the best support for any modification, the processes of economic convergence were first of all manifested and are being manifested in the financial sector. This, among other things, paid off.

The main form of joint business organization within the framework of inter-

segment and inter-industry convergence is a financial conglomerate - a form of integration of member firms from different segments of the financial market (inter-segment convergence). different segments and sectors of the economy (intersectoral convergence). It is aimed at increasing the competitiveness of these firms, which is carried out through their cooperation in the form of voluntary convergence or the voluntary but often aggressive penetration of one firm into another firm's activities. However, within the conglomerate itself, the option of combining firms - participants is determined by the model of their interaction. Among the most popular forms of convergence of activities of joint business participants with a voluntary form of implementation of inter-segment convergence: mutual cooperation of economic entities built by the initiator on the basis of a distribution agreement. convergence of passive participant's products and/or services; Mutual cooperation of business entities based on "Strategic Alliance" cooperation; mutual cooperation of business entities within the framework of a joint venture, including business entities in different segments of the financial market and aimed at creating specific (convergent) financial products - banking, insurance, investments; a business entity based on the use of a single brand mutual cooperation of entities; mutual cooperation of business entities within the financial supermarket; establishment of a new economic entity. Different from the above is the model of "interaction of economic entities, which is carried out in an aggressive form of its implementation and is based on the penetration of the initiator of rapprochement into the activities of his passive participant." New forms and models of doing business, as well as formats of mutual cooperation and cooperation of economic entities in the digital economy, are created taking into account the use of positive effects of digitalization and its products in business. Such new forms of doing business (even outside the processes of economic convergence, among them) it is necessary to study the features of its influence on the insurance market in order to study more deeply and consider digitalization as a factor of increasing the efficiency of insurance. , including Russian, review the advantages, opportunities and negative effects.

In this case, the main direction of using the new electronic database is the development of data-based business system models based on it. Naturally, more sophisticated digitization products have more opportunities to positively influence economic convergence processes at any level. This gives reason to believe that the most complex digitalization product will provide the greatest positive impact on the business implemented at a certain level of economic

convergence according to the criterion "Digitalization product with the greatest impact on joint business efficiency" - IT platforms and the networks that connect them. "The Nature of Convergence Initiator's Primary Product Linkage with Digital and Information Technologies."

Table 1

Classification of economic ecosystems based on "the nature of the relationship of the initial main product of the initiator of convergence with digital and information technologies".

The nature of connecting the initial main product of the convergence initiator with digital and information technologies	Ecosystem type
Not related to digital and information technology	Food (general type)
Based on the use of digital and/or information technologies	Digital
An independent digital product or information technology	Information Technology (IT)

The formation and development of economic ecosystems is significantly influenced by various factors, including digitization - the modern trend of social development. The use of specific digitization products related to the main stages of development provides special advantages for the development of joint business (including economic ecosystems), which can be manifested in the emergence, development and implementation of certain areas of increasing its efficiency. .

Digitization affects all parameters of economic convergence - prerequisites, factors and characteristics of the business model. This creates special opportunities for joint business initiators and participants to achieve the highest efficiency by implementing ways to increase its effectiveness due to the impact of digitalization on economic convergence (Table 2).

Table 2

Possible directions for improving joint business efficiency due to the impact of digitization on economic convergence

A type of economic convergence	Digitization product		
	IT	IT, IT platforms	IT, IT platforms and networks connecting them

Intrasegment	All areas of joint business efficiency improvement are carried out within the framework of intra-segment convergence using IT.	All areas of joint business efficiency improvement are implemented as part of intra-segment convergence using IT and IT platforms.	All areas of joint business efficiency improvement are carried out within the framework of intra-segment convergence using IT, IT platforms and their connecting networks.
Intersegment	All areas of joint business efficiency improvement are carried out within the framework of inter-segmental convergence using IT.	All areas of joint business efficiency improvement are implemented as part of cross-segment convergence using IT and IT platforms.	All areas of joint business efficiency improvement are carried out within the framework of inter-segmental convergence using IT, IT platforms and their connecting networks.
Network	All areas of increasing joint business efficiency are implemented within the framework of inter-industry convergence using IT.	All areas of joint business efficiency improvement are implemented within the framework of cross-industry convergence using IT and IT platforms.	All areas of increasing joint business efficiency are implemented within the framework of inter-industry convergence using IT, IT platforms and their connecting networks.

The list of joint business features (preconditions, factors, business model) is the same for any level of convergence, but their content is different depending on the level of economic convergence at which the joint business is implemented (intrasegment, intersegment). or intersecting). For the degree of convergence within a segment, the directions for improving efficiency are limited to only one segment - in which convergence occurs. For example, for the insurance segment, this direction includes the use of a new sales channel for insurance products or new customers-insured, and for the banking segment, the emergence of a new channel for selling banking products and attracting new customers can get by bringing the activity closer to another bank. At the segment level, a financial

product integrated into an activity. An example of a direction to increase the effectiveness of a joint business for the inter-sectoral level of economic convergence is the sale of banking products to all customers of the joint business. A prerequisite for any degree of convergence is the similarity of certain aspects of activity - the same product (insurance product - insurance contract) when organizing joint business at the intra-segment level, and at the inter-segment level - a prerequisite. similarity of customer base. is to sell banking products to all customers of the joint venture. A prerequisite for any degree of convergence is the similarity of certain aspects of activity - the same product (insurance product - insurance contract) when organizing joint business at the intra-segment level, and at the inter-segment level - a prerequisite. similarity of customer base. is to sell banking products to all customers of the joint venture. A prerequisite for any degree of convergence is the similarity of certain aspects of activity - the same product (insurance product - insurance contract) when organizing joint business at the intra-segment level, and at the inter-segment level - a prerequisite. similarity of customer base.

As mentioned above, digitalization has a special impact on the processes of economic convergence. It manifests itself through the use of different degrees of convergence in joint business of key digitization products, based on three main stages of development. Thus, the first stage of digitization development is characterized by the creation of separate IT, and the second stage uses IT platforms in addition to them. Networks of different levels developed and implemented in the third stage of digitalization development help to form a unified information space in business by uniting different platforms and individual IT. This is the most complex product of digitization in the third stage - IT, It indicates that IT platforms and their connecting networks are being created, which will ensure the creation of new forms of doing business. The impact of digitalization is manifested through the use of its main products and its impact on the main parameters of convergence - the prerequisites, factors and parameters of the business model. In order to implement (attract) all directions of digitalization, it is necessary to ensure the positive impact of digitalization products on all parameters of economic convergence at any level - conditions, factors and the business model itself. the secret is manifested through the use of its main products and the impact on the main parameters of convergence - the prerequisites, factors and parameters of the business model. In order to implement (attract) all directions of digitalization, it is necessary to ensure the positive impact of digitalization products on all parameters of

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In the case of using the same digitization product, the different content (content) of the conditions will cause it to have a different effect on economic convergence and, accordingly, have a different effect on increasing the efficiency of the joint business initiator and participants. The information presented in the table shows opportunities to improve joint business performance by influencing the content of digitalization product prerequisites such as IT and IT platforms. The above examples show that the application of this product at a high level of convergence leads to a wide range of opportunities to improve joint business performance. In turn, the complexity of the digitization product. For example, in addition to IT and IT platforms, the use of networks connecting them allows joint business customers to directly "access" all participants of the convergence. For the example shown in the table, with the intersectoral level of economic convergence, joint business customers will be able to receive medical and insurance services at the same time. Similar conclusions on the impact of digitization can be drawn on other characteristics of joint ventures (factors and business model parameters) that characterize different levels of economic convergence. for example, with the cross-sectoral level of economic convergence, joint business customers will be able to receive medical and insurance services at the same time. Similar conclusions on the impact of digitization can be drawn on other characteristics of joint ventures (factors and business model parameters) that characterize different levels of economic convergence. for example, with the cross-sectoral level of economic convergence, joint business customers will be able to receive medical and insurance services at the same time. Similar conclusions on the impact of digitization can be drawn on other characteristics of joint ventures (factors and business model parameters) that characterize different levels of economic convergence.

Table 3

The following digitalization products are possible options for improving joint business efficiency in the case of IT and platforms

Degree	The content of the building and its implementation joint venture	Effect result
Intrasegmentth initiator and participants - insurance companies)	The same customer base for convergence participants (customers insurance companies). In joint business, the customer base is formed according to customer information, participants convergence - insurance companies.	The use of a common database of customers of all insurance companies included in the joint business by all participants of the joint business makes it possible to sell insurance contracts to an expanded group of customers, which increases the volume of sales of insurance products and improves results. financial and economic activities of joint business and insurance industry participants in general.
Inter segment(initiat or - bank, participant insurance company)	Similarity of customer base (bank and insurance company). In a joint business, the customer base is formed according to the information of the customer, participants of the convergence - a bank and an insurance company.	The use of a common database of bank and insurance company clients included in the joint business by all participants of the joint business allows to sell banking, insurance and convergent banking and insurance products to an expanded group of clients. To increase their sales volume and improve financial and economic results, the participants of joint business activities, as well as the insurance and banking segments of the financial sector.

The previous analysis showed that the most advanced digitization product in joint business is IT, IT platforms and the networks that connect them. The use of this comprehensive digitization product for joint business within the framework of cross-industry economic convergence allows:

- implementation of the principle of "win-win" in joint business and, therefore, abandoning the aggressive form of attracting other participants to joint business;
- Voluntary involvement of various business entities that are technologically related to the business of the convergence initiator and are not related to it, suitable for joint business implementation within the framework of inter-sectoral economic convergence.

- creation of modified, combined and new products of all participants of the joint business offered to customers;
 - changing the customer-oriented strategy of the convergence initiator as a key element of any other strategy of the company;
 - providing the client with the opportunity to use a wide range of products and services of all participants of the joint business "here and now".
- Analysis of the possible impact of digitization on economic convergence processes - conditions, factors and business model, defines a list of possible ways to increase joint business efficiency.

The following should also be taken into account when determining the list of possible areas of improvement of joint business efficiency.

The independent and combined effect of the degree of convergence and digitalization products can have not only positive, but also certain negative consequences. Therefore, the formation of a complete list of possible directions for increasing the efficiency of joint business includes the following activities in advance:

- to identify all potential opportunities to increase efficiency in connection with the characteristics of the level of economic convergence and the use of a certain digital product, including relevant conditions, factors and the content of the business organization itself;
- identify possible negative consequences of economic convergence and digitization effects that may adversely affect joint business performance;
- development of management decisions aimed at reducing possible negative consequences;
- assessment of the possible actual result of the joint business, i.e. comparing the efficiency gains due to the possible positive effects of convergence and digitization with the decrease in efficiency due to the possible negative effects.

The result of this analysis will be a list of joint business activities, the development of which will increase its effectiveness.

Developed below an algorithm for creating an initial set of all possible routes to increase the efficiency of joint business, which is carried out within a certain level of convergence when using a specific digitalization product.

The sequence of actions of this algorithm includes the following four steps:

1. clarify the considered level of economic convergence for which the joint business will be established and the specific digitization product used within it;

2. define a list of prerequisites, factors and values of business model parameters for the level of convergence in question and the specific digitization product used in it;
3. determine the characteristics of the content of the necessary conditions, factors and parameters of the business model;
4. creating a list of all possible ways to increase joint business efficiency (based on the analysis of the content of the prerequisites, factors and parameters of the business model, taking into account the risk assessment of the interaction between economic convergence and digitization).).

The initial set obtained as a result of the presented algorithm is used to select specific directions for increasing business efficiency.

In general, the analysis showed the following.

The characteristics of the interaction between the level of convergence and digitization lead to different contents of the prerequisites, factors and parameters of the business model, which, in turn, determines the feasibility of clarifying their contents under the influence of different levels of economic convergence. various digital products. Convergence and digitization processes can affect joint business efficiency in different ways, so it is necessary to take this fact into account when forming a list of possible directions for increasing its efficiency.

In addition, the following should be noted. In general, since digitalization can have both positive and negative effects on the processes of economic convergence, this fact should be taken into account when identifying all possible directions for increasing efficiency. The real size of the positive effect of one or another direction of efficiency improvement, usually measured in monetary terms, between the potential, the maximum possible economic effect resulting from the introduction of the considered direction of efficiency improvement should be defined as a difference. costs associated with obtaining it. At the same time, the possible negative consequences measured in monetary units are a considered way to increase efficiency. should be taken into account among the costs of implementing the system, i.e. possible negative effects of digitization should be taken into account.

Later on. When choosing a criterion of joint business efficiency, the initiator first of all raises the question of whether the chosen criterion of efficiency ensures the achievement of its goal - to increase its competitiveness. This means that whatever criterion is chosen for joint business effectiveness, it should be related to solving the problem of increasing the competitiveness of the initiator of joint

business creation.

Additional requirements for building an effective joint venture include:

- business efficiency should be calculated taking into account not only positive, but also possible negative effects of digitalization on economic convergence processes;
- the search for the most effective methods of increasing efficiency should be based on all possible areas characterized by a certain degree of convergence, provided that a certain digital product is used in it.

As mentioned above, the list of all possible directions for improving business efficiency, determined by the content of the prerequisites, factors and parameters of the business model, is the interaction between a certain level of economic convergence and specific digitization. related to the characteristics of the secret. product. Note that the algorithm for creating an initial set of all possible directions for increasing business efficiency, which is carried out within a certain level of convergence when using a certain digitization product, includes:

- determining the level of economic convergence at which the joint venture will be established and the specific digitization product used within it;
 - determine the relevant list of prerequisites, factors and values of business model parameters;
 - determine the characteristics of the content of the determined conditions, factors and parameters of the business model;
- making a list of all possible ways to improve joint business efficiency.

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